

Vibration Isolator of Quasi-Zero Stiffness Metamaterials with High Load-Carrying Capacity and Self-Sensing

H. Hong¹, K.I. Jeong¹, W.K. Kim¹, M.A. Raja¹, and S.S. Kim¹

¹Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology, department of Mechanical Engineering
Mechanical Design Lab. with Advanced Materials

August, 2023.

Introduction

- Metamaterials:

Applications of Metamaterials

- Research objective

The quasi-zero stiffness characteristics can have outstanding vibration reduction capability

Therefore, the quasi-zero stiffness metamaterial with a high target load was created through machine learning-based optimization.

Numerical & Experimental Methods

- Design optimization using machine learning

- ✓ Considering both structural safety and quasi-zero stiffness characteristic, optimization was performed using a machine learning

- Fabrication of quasi-zero stiffness metamaterials

Results & Discussion

- Transmissibility vibration tests of QZS metamaterials with several preload

- Transient vibration tests of QZS metamaterial and rubber

- Self-sensing test of QZS metamaterial

